

WLCG Strategy 2024-2027

David Britton (University of Glasgow)

Simone Campana (CERN)

Tommaso Boccali (INFN Pisa)

on behalf of the WLCG Collaboration

The WLCG collaboration

The Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) is the global infrastructure developed and operated over the last two decades that provides the computing infrastructure for the processing and analysis of data from the LHC experiments. The WLCG Collaboration comprises the sites being part of the infrastructure and the LHC experiments¹, with a thin management layer. The notable achievement of WLCG has been to successfully meet the needs of the LHC experiments by the integration of globally distributed Exascale-level resources with services and software, within a trust framework that transcends site and national boundaries. WLCG is currently of the scale of over a million cores and more than an Exabyte of storage. It extends across 160 sites in over 40 countries and is underpinned by 65 Memoranda of Understanding signed by funding agencies across the world. The success of WLCG has relied on innovation, leadership, collaboration, agility, and the confidence of the community and funders to commit to the endeavour. The future brings new challenges in terms of scale, technology, funding, sustainability, and the growth of other related communities. Within this context, WLCG must develop a strategy to enact over the next four years to prepare for HL-LHC Run-4 that will bring a step change in the amount and complexity of the data that will need to be processed.

Over the next four years, WLCG must continue to:

- Support the core use cases (ongoing LHC) whilst evolving the infrastructure to meet the needs of the HL-LHC.
- Identify, explore, and exploit techniques to increase the output of the infrastructure without increasing the cost.
- Evolve services to benefit from advancing technologies, for example with a careful evaluation of in-house vs commercial tools.
- Optimise the person-power needed to operate the infrastructure.
- Increasingly embrace heterogeneous architectures and include diverse types of facilities.
- Develop methods to reduce our energy footprint and the CO2 emissions.
- Collaborate with other communities representing sciences, software, and digital infrastructures, to share R&D and operational aspects where mutually beneficial.

The WLCG strategy to achieve these objectives include:

¹ In this document we refer to ALICE, ATLAS, CMS and LHCb as the LHC experiments.

- Maintaining a focus on evolving and optimising current operations to deliver high availability resources to the LHC experiments. Our strategy implies continuity and continuous improvement.
- Reducing the cost, energy consumption, and carbon footprint of computing by being able to use a wide range of resources including Grid, public or private clouds, HPCs, and by expanding the architectures from the original x86 to include e.g. ARM, RISK-V, GPUs, and other technologies that may become available. Our strategy is to build agility so that opportunities can be seized.
- Modernising tools and services, benefiting from standards that are less HEP-specific where applicable. Our strategy is to profit where we can from well supported software that is used by the wider community.
- Ensuring continuity and evolution through a programme of data challenges and improved monitoring. Our strategy is to avoid the accumulation of technical debt but without introducing disruptive changes.
- Increasing collaboration with other communities, including formalising the status of associate partners in WLCG and increasing synergies with national and international initiatives developing large scale computing infrastructures. Our strategy is to benefit where we can from other relevant work.
- Reviewing the structure and governance of WLCG; set up bodies, boards, and task forces to address problems and issues. Our strategy is to focus and optimise our existing strengths.

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WLCG service operations

The WLCG service has reliably delivered the infrastructure to support the LHC experiments' computing needs since 2006. The WLCG sites provide services to the experiments with an

availability and reliability generally exceeding the MoU² targets. The volume of resources in WLCG (CPU, storage, network) has increased by more than one order of magnitude since the start of the LHC, with no degradation of the service efficiency and performance. Operations are a shared activity between the WLCG sites and the experiments with, in many cases, a large overlap. In addition, a small WLCG Operations Coordination team oversees activities and reports to the WLCG Management Board. The activities include both the day-to-day operations (e.g., addressing of issues and reviewing incidents and target metrics) and the execution of medium-term activities (e.g., upgrade campaigns, deployment of new features). The strong connection between experiments, sites and infrastructure providers allows WLCG to quickly react to rapidly changing conditions, as we have seen many times in the LHC physics program. The review committees (LHCC and C-RRB) regularly congratulate WLCG for the success in delivering computing services which fulfil the needs of the experiments.

The effort available for operations has decreased over recent years, both within the experiments and at sites. A non-conclusive discussion on this topic took place at the August 2021 LHCC. The WLCG stakeholders should consider different ways to attract additional effort in this area and to optimise the use of existing effort. Possible options include finding more synergies between stakeholders; innovating the tools and services in use to run operations; and reducing the complexity of some of the services. A dedicated initiative on this topic should be launched.

[OPS-1] WLCG to periodically examine (e.g., yearly) the effort to run operations. Investigate ways to further optimise the operational effort needed to run the infrastructure, services, and workflows.

WLCG technical evolution

The operational success of WLCG is based, in part, on a conservative approach to technical evolution. Since the facilities in WLCG are loosely coupled and the middleware development effort is distributed, new features are introduced to the infrastructure rather gradually to ensure continuity of operations. Examples are the multi-year plan for the transition from X509 to tokens and the decommissioning of SRM.

In terms of more disruptive innovation, there is sometimes resistance to changing a system that works. However, in the modern and rapidly evolving environment of distributed computing, WLCG risks accumulating additional technical debt if agility is not maintained. There are examples of initiatives put in place in preparation for HL-LHC, particularly in the area of Data Management (DOMA), that led to a successful R&D program, with short- and long-term benefits. Broadening the scope of modernisation of tools and services will be an essential ingredient for the future technical sustainability of the WLCG infrastructure. The capability to use different computing architectures will also play a key role.

² <https://wlcg.web.cern.ch/mou>

[TECH-1] WLCG to develop plans to broaden the scope of efforts to modernise tools and services as an essential ingredient for the future technical sustainability of the WLCG infrastructure.

WLCG should establish a structure that allows for innovation to take place without interrupting production operations. The Data Challenges in preparation for HL-LHC have, so far, been a successful initiative to commission the data management services at increasing scale, but also demonstrate the outcomes of R&D activities in a large-scale environment. The Data Challenge model should be retained. The program should be continued according to the established plan and expanded to more topics. Such a plan should be regularly reviewed to adapt to the potentially changing landscape.

[TECH-2] WLCG to develop/expand a structure for testing innovation, possibly based on the successful model of data challenges.

WLCG would benefit from more coordination in the technical evolution area. In particular, a technical coordination team should ensure a coherent process of modernisation of services. This process should build a technical evolution roadmap spanning from short term goals to long term ambitions. An approach where a series of topical blueprints is produced and followed by a set of demonstrators, has proved to be effective in our community and should be considered. While modernisation should be a continuous process, the challenges presented by HL-LHC deserve special attention. WLCG should consider producing a Technical Design Report based on the outcome of the demonstrators that will be most relevant for HL-LHC.

[TECH-3] WLCG to produce a technical roadmap for the ramp-up to HL-LHC in time to be useful for the start of Run-4. This document should serve to align the milestones of the experiments with the ones of the WLCG infrastructure.

[TECH-4] WLCG to set up an open Technical Forum (TF) and a Technical Coordination Board (TCB) to oversee evolution and innovation of services. The TCB main responsibility is to define a Technical Roadmap and ensure its implementation through the TF.

Financial sustainability of WLCG services and infrastructure

WLCG continues to receive strong support from its funding agencies, with resources being provided with a roughly constant yearly budget (the “flat budget model”). The improvements in hardware technology up to a few years ago, have ensured that more capacity - roughly 15% - could be committed each year to the experiments despite the flat budget. In addition, more resources are available to the experiments beyond the pledged capacity, particularly in case of CPUs, either from additional resources at the same sites, or use of the experiment trigger-farms when available, or via the utilisation of external cloud and HPC centres, via opportunistic and managed patterns. The federations and their funding agencies have also been responsive in providing further resources when unforeseen or unprecedented circumstances have occurred (e.g., in 2016 with the unprecedented performance of the LHC; in 2023 with the uncertainties

caused by the war in Ukraine). The processes established in the context of the C-RRB have ensured that pledged resources could be delivered in time for the start of the LHC run each year, even in years of very volatile markets. The newly established channel between WLCG, the LHCC and the CRSG now offers the opportunity to better understand how resource availability impacts the scientific program. There is generally a good dialog and a trust relationship between experiments, funding agencies, federations, sites, and WLCG management.

Several financial challenges have been identified:

- Globally, HEP budgets are not expanding significantly and LHC computing is likely to continue to be operated in the flat-funding mode of the last decade.
- In several federations, the same budget needs to cover costs that are increasing over time (e.g. infrastructure and electricity).
- The hardware markets in the last five years have not been very favourable, which has limited the increase in the amount of resources that could be purchased year-on-year.

To assure the financial sustainability of the WLCG infrastructure, several pillars have been identified:

- The evolution of hardware and market trends need to be monitored more closely. Formalising a medium to long-term outlook of these trends (e.g. up to five years) will inform decisions about the areas of development in which the WLCG community should invest. WLCG should identify the appropriate structure to monitor these trends, globally and at national level.

[FIN-1] WLCG to identify the appropriate structure to monitor hardware and market trends, globally and at national level.

- Some of the federations have the opportunity to profile the budget for computing over many years. WLCG should regularly produce a multi-year (e.g., 5 and 10 years) outlook of the resource needs in addition to the current yearly estimates through the C-RSG process. The multi-year predictions should be accurate enough for the federations and their funding agencies to profile the future spending within a few tens of percent of uncertainty.

[FIN-2] WLCG to facilitate, harmonise and guide the development of a multi-year resource planning.

- The commitments of the federations are expected to be flat over the financial year (same level of resources from April to March). This prevents opportunities such as providing pledged capacity, and particularly CPUs at low cost for a limited number of months. Examples are opportunities from special HPC allocations or Cloud contracts. At the same time, the current model allows the experiments to predict the amount of resources that will be available, and to benefit from the required flexibility to use them. A model which allows

bursty allocations to be provided, while not impacting the core business of the experiments, should be considered as complementary to the flat allocations.

[FIN-3] WLCG to consider evolving the pledge mechanism to enable contributions from time-limited allocations.

- Considerable middleware development of the services in use in WLCG is contributed by the institutes in the Collaboration. These contributions are not formally agreed nor acknowledged. To reduce the operational risk linked to these services, a more formal process for collecting these contributions should be considered. It would also acknowledge and recognise the commitments of the institutes beyond providing hardware capacity, hopefully helping them to secure funding for development and support of the middleware. This process could start by simply collecting the information on existing efforts and reviewing it regularly. In a second phase, the commitments could be made more formal, e.g. through an MoU or a Collaboration Agreement.

[FIN-4] WLCG to identify a way to recognise the commitments (or list the contributions) from sites, federations and funding agencies for middleware development and support.

Heterogeneous Grid infrastructure

The role of the WLCG Tier-0, Tier-1s and Tier-2s

The organisation of WLCG facilities as Tier-0, Tier-1s and Tier-2s offers a simple but effective way to define the expected quality-of-service and target metrics specified in the WLCG MoU. The experiments can base the organisation of the data and the execution of the workflows on such quality of services. The resources are pledged according to the tier hierarchy, providing a simple model for experiment and federations to agree on the commitments.

The Tier-0 and Tier-1s constitute the core data archive and delivery infrastructure. While the network topology is today more flexible than originally anticipated, the connectivity across Tier-0 and Tier-1s is provided through dedicated links (the Optical Private Network - OPN). This guarantees enough capacity for the time-critical use cases. The vast majority of remaining links between Tier-1s and Tier-2s are provided by the LHCONE overlay network, ensuring separation of the traffic from other sciences in the Research and Education networks. The network infrastructure is one of the main assets in WLCG, enabling its core functions.

The simple organisation of WLCG facilities in three tiers also has drawbacks and it is partially obsolete in the sense that it was designed to address network limitations that largely no longer exist. Sites exchange data as a full mesh rather than hierarchically. Within the same tier type, the capabilities that sites offer can be very different. The experiments would benefit from being exposed more directly to these capabilities. It would allow them to better shape the computing

model and operations and take advantage of these capabilities. However, introducing a more complicated process to request resources with some capability, is not felt as appropriate. WLCG could, however, regularly collect the information about site capabilities (e.g. memory per core, I/O, bandwidth from/to tape, size of buffers), for example as part of the C-RRB preparation, and expose them to the experiments. This would build the basis for a possible future model where resources are discussed not just in terms of volume but also capability.

[INFRA-1] WLCG to investigate mechanisms to collect, organise and expose information about site capabilities (compute, storage, network).

Integration of Cloud resources in WLCG

The WLCG experiments started using resources provided directly through cloud interfaces more than 10 years ago. The focus has generally been on CPU rather than storage. There are also successful examples of integration of cloud storages into the experiment data management stack. Over the years, several models for the use of cloud-provided CPUs were demonstrated. The cloud resources could be integrated as an expansion of an existing facility (T1 or T2), or access could be granted through a gateway service (e.g. HEPCloud), or the cloud native interface was integrated directly with the experiment workload (and data) management system (e.g. the recent ATLAS project with a major commercial cloud provider). Some of the WLCG experiments also expose their HLT resources through a cloud interface to use the compute-power of the online facility outside data-taking periods. The possibility to integrate commercial and academic/private resources with WLCG services allowed the experiments to benefit from considerable beyond-pledge capacity. The progress made in the WLCG benchmarking with the HEPSCORE deployment now facilitates comparison of commercial cloud resources with CPUs at WLCG sites.

The opportunities offered by cloud resources and the integration of cloud services into WLCG has never been pursued at an holistic level. More opportunities could be exploited in future by making progress in several areas:

- An increasing number of WLCG federations have expressed an interest in committing resources through an academic cloud infrastructure. This would allow them to support a single multipurpose platform for many academic use-cases including HEP. For this to happen, some technical progress should be made. At the very least, it should be understood how these resources can be properly monitored and accounted for, as they would not expose Grid middleware and services. Some recipes for integrating cloud resources with different interfaces should also be defined and shared. This work would also be beneficial for integrating commercial cloud resources.

[INFRA-2] WLCG to collect information and document the technical solutions used to integrate and procure cloud resources with WLCG.

- The integration of commercial clouds in WLCG, or more generally with the production and data management systems of the experiments, has occurred in rather isolated cases. In

various instances, an analysis of the costs was made and in recent activities, an attempt was made to compare them with the costs of running services at a WLCG site. The cost of cloud resources is very dependent on boundary conditions, the contact with the cloud vendor and the workflows being executed. The connection via National Research and Education networks is also a factor to consider. In some federations, there are additional financial hurdles because there are no mechanisms to spend capital hardware funding to pay for an on-going service provision. WLCG would benefit from a blueprint for the integration of commercial cloud resources and an activity tracking the costs in different scenarios. A recent blueprint³ was produced specifically for the US, and it could be extended to cover other regions in WLCG. In addition, some scientific communities (e.g., LSST) with slightly different use cases than HEP have moved to a model where cloud resources play a central role in providing storage and compute capabilities to the end users. While not completely applicable to HEP, WLCG should follow the progress and learnings of these communities and retain what is appropriate.

[INFRA-3] WLCG to establish channels allowing to follow the progress of other communities exploiting clouds.

- There has been little use of cloud storage so far, although cloud storage interfaces have been integrated in the data management system of the experiments. While there is a risk in relying on cloud resources for data processing, the risks to consider when relying on cloud resources for storage - in particular when applied to Tier-1 sites (e.g. vendor lock-in) which are the storage backbone of WLCG - are larger. There may also be issues around open-data access policies to consider. There is no such a thing as a WLCG cloud usage policy and the collaboration should consider defining one.

[INFRA-4] WLCG to define a provisioning policy for sites intending to provide storage via commercial clouds that ensures the conditions of the MoU are met.

- The benefits from a model where part of the pledged resources could be provided for a limited number of months in a year were described in the financial sustainability section above. They apply well to provisioning through commercial cloud resources.

Integration of HPC resources in WLCG

The HEP use cases have little technical need for High Performance Computing *per se* - there is little or no use of, or need for, MPI applications. At the same time, the embarrassingly parallel nature of HEP workflows is such that these workflows can easily profit from available cycles in a HPC machine. WLCG computing is not elective science; it is a deterministic and long-term requirement of the approved LHC physics programme. In this sense, it does not fit well with shorter-term competitive grant processes used to allocate time on many HPC machines. Pledges

³ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.07376>

need to be established well in advance and delivery guaranteed. However, some HPC resources have been integrated into WLCG for many years and in some cases (e.g., the NDGF Tier-1 and more recently the INFN Tier-1) part of the pledged capacity *is* provided through cycles from HPCs, completely integrated behind the Grid middleware. This allows the experiments to benefit from these resources transparently. In most cases however, the integration of the HPC system happens through a central gateway (e.g in the case of HEPCloud) or directly with the experiment workload management system (Alien, Condor GlideinWMS, Dirac, Panda). Specific HPC systems have demonstrated the ability to provide a large amount of opportunistic resources to the experiments. In specific cases, and for limited periods of time, the scale of these resources has been comparable to the pledges in WLCG, though provided opportunistically.

The HPC machines are heterogeneous in many respects. The interfaces to the machines can vary and the policy to access the resources are specific to each HPC centre. Some are permissive and similar to a WLCG site, some others are restrictive and difficult to access in an efficient way. The CPU hardware deployed by the HPC centres is not always x86 (e.g. some centres deploy Power or ARM and, in the near future RISC-V). In addition, a large fraction of the processing capacity at HPC centres today is provided with GPUs. Using these architectures requires a considerable investment in software development for the experiments and the communities supporting the common libraries (see next section). In addition, the algorithms need to be validated to ensure the physics results are not dependent on the architecture being used. At the same time, some federations expect in future to commit part of the capacity in the form of cycles at HPC centres and are inviting WLCG to take the necessary steps to ensure these resources can be used efficiently. Today this is not the case and the HPC centres are generally used for a limited number of use-cases and in an opportunistic fashion. Some HPCs are simpler to integrate, providing the most benefit for the the effort invested. In order to make progress, WLCG needs to work in several areas:

- At the technical level, there are solutions that are known to work that integrate HPC systems with the experiments' workload management systems. These solutions are often experiment-specific, but several of the building blocks are common. WLCG should produce a blueprint for the integration of HPC systems and describe a reference implementation based on these building blocks. This can also be used when liaising with the management of these centres to explain our needs. It should also explain which policies at the HPC centres would simplify the integration work if implemented or relaxed, and which are a “no-go” for resource utilisation. A recent blueprint was produced specifically for the US⁴ and experiment specific documents on the use of HPCs also exist⁵. These documents can be extended to cover other experiments and/or regions in WLCG. They should also cover the technical requirements of the experiments.

⁴ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.07376>

⁵ https://cds.cern.ch/record/2707937/files/NOTE2020_003.pdf and https://cds.cern.ch/record/2707936/files/NOTE2020_002.pdf

[INFRA-5] WLCG to document technical requirements and existing solutions to integrate HPC centres and organise a knowledge base. Where possible, this should propose one or more reference implementations via blueprint documents.

- At the executive level, a stronger relationship needs to be established between WLCG and the HPC centres. Good progress was made at the national level through the relationship between some of the Tier-1 facilities and HPC centres. Both in Europe and the US, WLCG needs to construct a dialogue with the federations and funding agencies to drive the future allocation policies at HPC sites. Multi-year allocations for example would be highly beneficial and needed for proper planning in WLCG. Opportunistic access of HPC resources for beyond pledge use should also be better negotiated.

[INFRA-6] WLCG to construct, where useful, a dialogue with the federations, funding agencies, and the relevant global bodies to drive the future allocation policies at HPC sites.

- The strong relationship mentioned above should be levered to discuss the architecture of future HPC centres. So far, such architectures do not typically favour data-intensive sciences, but this is about to change and HEP has the opportunity to contribute with its decades of experience in suggesting the most suitable future architectures. Initiatives such as ETP4HPC⁶ and the EU funded project SPECTRUM⁷ focus on this. It is also important to build a good relationship with the teams responsible to implement and operate the HPC machines as it was demonstrated in several of the most successful cases of HPC use for LHC computing.

[INFRA-7] WLCG to influence the architecture of future HPC centres by leveraging the relationship with the HPC centres and with the funding agencies, and via interactions with the relevant international bodies.

The three items mentioned above should be part of a HPC WLCG strategy that should be produced in the next year. This work should happen in synergy with other data-intensive sciences. In Europe, there is an opportunity to do so in the context of a recent Joint ECFA-NuPECC-APPEC (JENAA) initiative, in time for the next European Strategy for Particle Physics.

Several projects are being proposed in EU, USA and other contexts to sketch future directions in the collaboration between the HPC ecosystem and scientific domains. WLCG should encourage and foster the participation of its members to such projects, in order to guarantee the visibility and the coverage of its present and future needs.

[INFRA-8] WLCG to monitor the projects on national and global scale designing collaboration strategies for the collaboration with HPCs and foster the participation of its members.

⁶ <https://www.etp4hpc.eu/pujades/files/ETP4HPC%20SRA%203%20-%20Single%20Page%20-%201.pdf>

⁷ The project will start in Jan 2024 and will deliver a Strategic Research, Innovation and Deployment Agenda (SRIDA) which defines the innovation and deployment roadmap for data-intensive science and infrastructures.

Analysis Facilities

The discussion about specialised facilities for end-user analysis has been taking place under the umbrella of the HEP Software Foundation (HSF) for several years. Some large projects, for example IRIS-HEP, have developed an ecosystem for interactive analysis and the functionalities of this ecosystem are being demonstrated through a set of challenges. The ROOT framework is also investing effort enabling the use of modern technologies for analysis. WLCG established links with these initiatives in the context of data management through the WLCG DOMA activity. This relationship, however, needs to be strengthened as the future development of the analysis facilities concept will likely have an impact on WLCG; we expect many of these facilities to be co-hosted with a WLCG site and share resources and services. The role of specialised facilities for Machine Learning, for example, have been only superficially discussed in WLCG and the resources for these activities have been provided opportunistically by some of the sites. In future, however, we expect the needs for ML/AI may increase both in terms of volume of resources but also variety of services. WLCG should therefore explore how such a facility could be hosted synergically with WLCG services. At the same time, we are aware that such facilities are being designed and will be operated in many national environments, and WLCG should be able to profit from their processing capabilities.

[INFRA-9] WLCG to explore how services and hardware supporting future analysis models could be hosted synergically with WLCG services.

General areas of work towards a more heterogeneous Grid infrastructure

- Progress should be made in several areas of the LHC offline software (common libraries and experiment specific software) to be able to lever the heterogeneous architectures offered by the HPC systems. Tools and solutions for heterogeneous computing are still an evolving ecosystem, with projects being started and retired. A technology tracking and evaluation activity (at the level of WLCG and beyond) would benefit the experiments by sharing experience and findings. From the infrastructure side, WLCG needs to prepare for heterogeneous compute architectures (e.g. GPUs) being provided to complement the x86 and non-x86 CPU hardware. This has already needed to be started in the context of HPC facilities, but it applies to all kinds of facilities, and will soon apply generally. While the main challenge is at the level of offline software, a progressive strategy also needs to be put in place at the infrastructure level. Measuring the use of CPU and GPU resources in hybrid systems should be the first step. This will require progress both in the benchmarking area and in the accounting tools and services. This work should be prioritised as in future these systems will likely be part of the pledge.

[INFRA-10] WLCG to prepare for heterogeneous compute architectures: facilitate the development of the offline software and make progress with benchmarking and accounting.

- WLCG needs to modernise services and protocols to benefit from modern standards that are increasingly less HEP specific, while retaining the advantages of the specific services developed by our community that are tailored to our use cases. WLCG already started moving successfully to less HEP specific protocols, such as HTTP/WebDAV for data management. The adoption of new standards implies decommissioning some of the existing protocols to ensure maintainability. WLCG should build a (better) process for this as legacy services and protocols tend to be difficult to eliminate in our infrastructure, and this increases the operational burden.

More progress should be made evaluating and possibly integrating widely adopted open-source products as building blocks of WLCG services. An example is Kubernetes, for which an initiative started in WLCG but did not progress to the level one would have hoped. The introduction of more external dependencies into the WLCG service stack obviously introduces potential risks. The risks should be properly identified, evaluated, catalogued and managed - see the following section about a risk catalogue. Existing initiatives at WLCG sites were already established to evaluate the risks from external software dependencies. The finding of these initiatives should be reused rather than launching a WLCG-specific process.

[INFRA-11] WLCG to establish a process for adopting modern, non-HEP specific standards where appropriate and decommission legacy services and protocols. The process should include risk management for external dependencies.

- WLCG should carefully follow the evolution of facilities that is currently happening at the national level. Ideally this process could reduce the cost in operating services and create opportunities for service managers to engage in new initiatives and/or contribute supporting the services while the hardware is located at other facilities. For example, solutions have been proposed for the data management of HL-LHC data and processing. WLCG should monitor closely its design, implementation, and testing, via the DOMA initiative and the planned data challenges, in order to validate it as a viable solution well before the start of Run-4. In general, the process towards consolidation needs to be adiabatic as the professional profile of the service managers will change (less HEP-oriented) and we need to allow for enough time for this to happen. The process also needs a proper narrative to avoid demoting the current experts or passing a message to the federations or funding agencies that less effort is required.

[INFRA-12] WLCG to follow and accommodate the national plans related to consolidating facilities, particularly where aimed at reducing complexity. WLCG should also engage the service managers in the transition and retain expertise.

Relationship with other HEP and non-HEP communities

WLCG today is the infrastructure to support the needs of the LHC experiments and this should remain its core mission. At the same time, it is strategically important for WLCG to ensure its scope is not too narrow around the core mission, in order to guarantee sustainability and continued support. WLCG should position itself as a science-driven organisation that provides services to HEP, but creates an ecosystem of tools, services, and capabilities useful to many other sciences. This will motivate the funding agencies to continue investing in WLCG as there will be a return of investment for other sciences. Depending on the sciences in question, and how close they are to the core mission of WLCG, the level of engagement will differ.

The WLCG funding agencies also support other experiments in HEP, NP and in some cases astronomy. Many of these large-scale experiments are organised in global collaborations motivating a distributed computing model and this will be more the case for the future. There is an interest in HENP in not duplicating the infrastructure for scientific computing but rather using a common set of tools and services, with the flexibility to complement them with experiment-specific ones. WLCG is seen as a model of a large-scale distributed scientific computing infrastructure, and many HENP experiments express willingness to collaborate with WLCG and adopt its services or a large set of them. WLCG sees this as an opportunity to enhance its sustainability by building a larger pool of contributors and not diverting effort of the community into supporting many solutions. The vision to enlarge the WLCG infrastructure to serve the needs of a larger number of HENP projects and other sciences, was presented at the ESPP in 2019 and at Snowmass in 2022. Different possibilities were discussed in the Collaboration concerning the governance of such an infrastructure. The governance model that has been implemented is very lightweight: experiments can become WLCG associate partners by presenting their use cases to the WLCG Management Board and motivating the interest to join the Collaboration. Today, DUNE, Belle-II JUNO and VIRGO are WLCG associate partners and participate in the technical evolution of WLCG and its operations. They are invited to the Management Board and the Grid Deployment Board. The current governance and partnership model works well but as we adapt to working with new groups it would be appropriate to define the following more formally:

- The process should be more structured, and the endorsement should be done at a higher level than the WLCG MB (e.g. at the WLCG CB).
- The criteria for becoming an associate partner should also be better clarified: there has to be an interest of the WLCG institutes in supporting an experiment as WLCG partner and there has to be a large enough overlap between the WLCG services and what the partner would like to use.
- The resource needs of the partner communities are expected to be small compared to the LHC experiments. The impact on resources should also be evaluated and monitored as part of the process. This is particularly true for networks especially if the connectivity would be provided by the LHCONE.

[REL-1] WLCG to formalise the process to become associate partner including: ratification moved to a higher body than the MB; clarification of the criteria; and evaluation of the impact on resources.

Other sciences, particularly Astronomy and Astroparticle Physics, also are interested in using several of the WLCG technologies and services. Some sharing of the infrastructure can be expected but the engagement of these communities with WLCG is more at the level of technologies. It is important that WLCG continues collaborating with these communities and lever initiatives such as JENA and ESCAPE in Europe, the DOE programs in the US, and partnering with OSG and EGI (see next section).

Relationship between WLCG and OSG, EGI and other (inter)national grid initiatives

OSG in the US and EGI in Europe have been WLCG partners since they were created. Both OSG and EGI provide federating services in use by WLCG and other sciences. The relationship between WLCG and EGI and the mutual benefits are described in a whitepaper⁸. The main areas of collaboration between the three entities are:

- The coordination of cybersecurity across the WLCG infrastructure (policies, threat intelligence and incident response). This collaboration is essential to ensure the proper level of security in a complex distributed ecosystem such as WLCG where local policies have precedence over the global ones.
- The provisioning of federating services such as Accounting, User Support, and the Information System. There is no WLCG common funding that would normally support the provisioning of these services. The mechanisms offered by EGI and OSG provide a solution. It is important therefore that this collaboration continues to ensure transparent access and use of the services for the communities.
- The support of middleware distributions: packaging, certification, and deployment. Both OSG and EGI contribute to the deployment of services in the WLCG infrastructure. In the case of OSG, it coordinates the deployment activity across US sites. This is partially true for EGI as well.
- Facilitate the dialog with middleware providers. For example, OSG is the main point of contact between WLCG and the HTCondor team.
- Support innovation of services across the infrastructure. EGI has been very successful in engaging with the European Commission and attracting funding for the benefit of its members. OSG is heavily involved in R&D initiatives such as IRIS-HEP in the US and receives funding to introduce modern and disruptive technologies in the infrastructure. WLCG has enjoyed considerable benefits from these funding streams.

There is a strategic interest for WLCG to continue its relationship with OSG and EGI. Both have been successful engaging the long tail of science and enabling them to access resources with a moderate investment of effort. WLCG should continue to leverage the collaboration with OSG and EGI to ensure that its service ecosystem is useful also for other sciences that are not its main partners.

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/4717751>

At the same time, the interaction and interdependency between EGI, OSG and WLCG services should be reviewed regularly. More coordination between the three parties would be beneficial to build a common roadmap and ensure the sustainability of the whole ecosystem. The WLCG management should have a leading role organising this process.

The dependency of WLCG on other partners also introduces risks that need to be evaluated regularly and mitigated. The sustainability model of OSG and EGI are rather different and WLCG should ensure operations are secured also in the case one of the partner initiatives faces funding issues. The section about financial sustainability suggests strengthening the commitments of the funding agencies and institutes for software development. The same should happen here for federating services provisioning, to mitigate the above-mentioned risks.

The benefits highlighted above apply to most countries in WLCG. A limited number of countries however see less advantages in being part of a federated grid infrastructure such as EGI, but still are willing to provide resources to WLCG experiments. These countries must be able to join the collaboration and provide resources, and it should be a priority of WLCG to negotiate particularly with EGI the conditions for this to happen.

[REL-2] WLCG to regularly review the interaction and interdependency with OSG and EGI and strengthen coordination across the three parties. OSG and EGI should be properly involved in [TECH-3] and [TECH-4].

[REL-3] WLCG to ensure that operations are secured in case one of the partner initiatives faces funding issues.

[REL-4] WLCG to promote the benefits of being part of EGI (or OSG) while ensuring that ultimately partners can join the collaboration and provide resources even if not part of EGI (or OSG).

Other actors are appearing in the landscape of (scientific) computing:

- EuroHPC Joint Undertaking has taken a driving role for the funding and operations of HPC centres in Europe, largely replacing PRACE;
- The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) wants to coordinate and organise national FAIR data infrastructures and allow for interoperability and service management via a core of federating services and a larger marketplace of thematic and general-purpose services.
- GAIA-X wants to develop a digital governance that can be applied to any existing cloud/ edge technology stack to obtain transparency, controllability, portability and interoperability across data and services, for the benefits of the productive system.

[REL-5] WLCG to look for synergies with the national and international initiatives developing large scale computing infrastructures.

(Offline) software and middleware development: relationship between WLCG and the development communities

The functioning of WLCG relies on middleware services connecting the high-level applications with the core services - e.g. compute, storage - at the sites. The high-level applications are normally developed by the experiments and implement experiment specific policies and functionalities. The middleware development in the past benefitted from funding from European and US sources, aimed at providing general services for a large number of sciences. These sources of funding partially drained away, particularly in Europe. Today a lot of the middleware development is supported by institutes and teams in HEP or with strong links to HEP. The great commitment and success of these teams supporting middleware development for the WLCG Collaboration and other sciences, is notable. The challenge is how to make this sustainable.

- Distributed computing is nowadays largely adopted by many communities. There are many large open-source projects providing solutions that could and are being adopted by WLCG. The technical coordination team proposed above in this document should oversee the technology trends, understand which solutions would be useful for WLCG and define an innovation plan to evaluate these solutions, measure the benefits and possibly introduce them in production, and minimise the effort needed to run the infrastructure. At the same time, the risks should be evaluated and properly taken into account. This modernisation process would make the WLCG service portfolio more appealing and usable for other sciences and it would therefore be a step forward also in the ambition to provide a multi-science infrastructure.
- WLCG should work with the partners providing today's middleware solutions and help them secure the funding to continue this work. This can happen in different ways and could be specific for each partner. The strategic directions proposed in the “Financial Sustainability” and “Impact of WLCG on science and society” sections of this document should however apply in general and would be a good starting point.

The offline software, for example the event generation, simulation, reconstruction, analysis, and its evolution, is a key ingredient for the success of the LHC program. A large fraction of the offline software is experiment specific. The development is a responsibility of the experiments and is supported by the institutes in the experiments. Another significant part of the offline software is more common and serves all experiments. This is the case, for example, for Geant4, ROOT, and the event generators produced by the theoretical community. The common software libraries evolve in line with the needs of the experiments and in collaboration with the experiments. The communities supporting the common software libraries are very heterogeneous. Some have solid grounding in the major WLCG institutes and labs, while others (e.g. the event generators) do not have a focus point. Progress in the area of offline software has a large impact on WLCG and is one of the main factors impacting the future resource needs of the experiments, both in volume and type. The experiments and the communities supporting the common software libraries have an excellent track record of software improvements that allowed a better use of the resources in

the WLCG infrastructure. WLCG has a strategic interest in facilitating this process and ensuring the process is properly organised.

[SOFT-1] WLCG to continue encouraging the necessary offline software improvements to make the best use of the infrastructure, while not being in charge of such a development.

The HSF was established to support and organise this process. The HSF made very good progress in many areas, recognised by our review bodies. The loose structure of the HSF, with minimal governance, supports the community building and creates an excellent forum for discussion. It does not offer the tools for rapid decision-making processes, which happen instead through natural selection. While exploring different avenues is important, a trade-off between fulfilling the needs of the community and not losing focus is needed. The natural selection needs to come primarily from the experiments, with input from WLCG as a whole.

[SOFT-2] WLCG to engage with the HSF to optimise the program of software development for the WLCG community.

Several national and international software projects today support the needs of the LHC experiments. There is little coordination across those projects as the funding structure is different for each one of them, and HEP is not always the only focus. Forming a coordinating body on top of these projects is unrealistic. WLCG could create however a mechanism for which PIs of current large projects or influential visionaries for new projects can discuss with the experiments and generally WLCG on the main strategic directions. The focus should be on the LHC needs, while the outcome should also serve the other communities. WLCG should ensure that the core goals of its community are well-understood and can influence the future directions. The focus should be on the HL-LHC program but the vision on new projects should also consider how to bring early benefits.

[SOFT-3] WLCG to consider creating a mechanism by which PIs of current large projects, or influential visionaries for new projects, can discuss the main strategic directions with the experiments and WLCG. .

Engagement and Governance

The success of the WLCG Collaboration is based on building consensus between all parties: the experiments, sites, middleware and service providers, and the national and international scientific computing initiatives. This consensus allows the implementation of an infrastructure of loosely coupled facilities offering the capabilities that the experiments need. The consensus building in WLCG has succeeded very well so far and the WLCG governance structure must continue to support this decision-making process. The governance also needs to evolve together with the Collaboration and its level of maturity, while the goal of building consensus needs to remain a core objective. The WLCG governance should be reviewed with these principles in mind. Areas to consider include:

- The LCG Project Leader is today (1) the leader of the WLCG Collaboration and (2) the leader of the CERN LCG project. The two roles are not the same but (2) is there to ensure that CERN's commitments to WLCG are fulfilled, particularly with respect to the support of the collaboration as a whole, in addition to the T0 capabilities. Today the two roles are coupled, and it is useful to have them coupled.
- There is an overlap of functions between the Grid Deployment Board and the WLCG Operations Coordination activity. There are fewer discussions about deployment than in the past as the infrastructure has reached a considerable level of maturity. At the same time there is no Technical Coordination Board to organise the discussion about the evolution of WLCG services. WLCG should consider re-scoping the GDB into a Technical Coordination and Deployment board, with a different mandate and an extended participation.
- The Management Board is in charge of the execution of the WLCG functions. It is *de facto* a very open meeting - open attendance, open material - and that helps the consensus building. It also limits the level of discussion on specific topics. WLCG should define the proper structure to discuss some topics in a more restricted environment, while keeping the current benefits of an open Management Board meeting.
- WLCG has demonstrated its capability to tactically address the computing needs of the experiments. There is no structured process, however, to define and endorse the more strategic aspects. This role is today partially covered by the Management Board, but it is not in its mandate and does not have the right representation from the Collaboration. The Collaboration Board would be the natural environment where items concerning the WLCG strategic directions are discussed, engaging experiments and sites. The strategic directions would be presented periodically to the Overview Board for endorsement. Several of the strategic items discussed above in this document should be a matter of discussion at the Collaboration Board. Examples are the cases of federations not delivering to WLCG as expected; discussions about new policies for pledging resources; policies for integrating non-grid facilities into WLCG (eg.clouds and HPCs); aspects related to membership of the collaboration; and relationships with partner infrastructures.

[GOV-1] WLCG to review its governance to better support this strategy, while preserving the “principle of consensus”. Areas to consider include project leadership, OB, MB, GDB, CB and TCB.

Environmental sustainability: energy efficiency, green computing, carbon footprint

Environmental sustainability is a strategic area of priority for many of the WLCG federations and funding agencies. WLCG started a process to estimate the energy consumption needed by the computing equipment for the LHC experiments. A study was produced in 2023 and presented at

the CHEP2023 conference⁹. Such a study analysed the main factors impacting the energy needs of WLCG and predicted the trend for the remainder of the LHC programme. GridPP also studied in detail the energy efficiency of different CPU architectures and the benefits for the experiments and sites if the software could be ported to these architectures. Providing information, opportunity, and incentive to help collaborators reduce the carbon footprint of computing needs should be a priority for WLCG as it is a priority of its funding agencies and a demonstration of social responsibility. WLCG should elaborate a plan that covers the areas of software, computing models, facilities, and hardware lifecycle. The progress needs to be regularly measured and exposed and the proper metrics need to be defined. Particularly in the area of improving energy efficiency of the facilities, WLCG cannot mandate a schedule to the countries but should collect information and track the progress.

[ENV-1] WLCG to agree on metrics and provide a framework to collect information related to energy efficiency.

[ENV-2] WLCG to facilitate the use of more energy-efficient hardware where possible, depending on the readiness of the experiment software and the common libraries.

[ENV-3] WLCG to develop and promote a sustainability plan to improve energy efficiency and reduce carbon footprint, covering software, computing models, facilities, and hardware technology and lifecycle.

Identify and review Risks and Mitigations

Several sections of this document highlight possible risks for WLCG and suggest defining mitigations. WLCG went through the process of identifying and analysing the main risks in 2020, assessing them in terms of impact and likelihood to define their severity. These were catalogued in a risk register, together with possible mitigations, and have been periodically reviewed at the WLCG Overview Board,. The structure of WLCG does not allow a formal risk management process due to the loose relationship between the partners. In that sense, CERN accepts the risk that computing is organised through WLCG rather than being uniquely a host lab responsibility. WLCG should continue reviewing the risk register at least once per year and present it to the Overview Board.

[RISK-1] WLCG to continue reviewing the risk register at least once per year and present it to the Overview Board for endorsement.

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202429504001>

Impact of WLCG on science and society, training, and outreach

The role of WLCG in scientific computing allowed various countries to develop a research and education cyber-infrastructure for the benefit of other sciences. The clearest example is the network infrastructure that WLCG had to develop to support increasingly challenging needs. There are still regions in WLCG where the network is not as good as one would hope but the network consortia and NRENs supporting WLCG are expanding on them. WLCG has not always been effective at communicating its value and the benefits of a new region or site joining the collaboration. WLCG does not really have a communication plan or a communication officer. Because of that, many successes of the collaboration go unnoticed.

[IMPACT-1] WLCG to establish a proper structure for communication and develop a communication strategy that is reviewed periodically by the collaboration.

It is relatively easy today for a site to get into WLCG from the technical perspective if the site is supported by a structure in the same country or region. In some countries however, the cyber-infrastructure for research and education is less developed. There is no central WLCG team supporting the installation and configuration of a new site. The experiments have an interest to support the academic environment in these countries but are not resources to support the installation of WLCG services. WLCG needs a strategy for supporting new countries willing to volunteer with limited resources. While there might be a limited return of investment from the pure hardware capacity perspective, broadening the scope to new countries should be seen as part of the social mission of WLCG and CERN to support science by enlarging their horizons. For this pursuit, WLCG should aim at reviving some of the support programs that existed in the past, leveraging also national and international partnering initiatives. For example, OSG and EGI conferences are a good opportunity for training service managers on established and new technologies. The same could be considered at HEPIX meetings. Evolving WLCG services and using less HEP-specific protocols, tools and services would facilitate the process and is therefore of major importance.

[IMPACT-2] WLCG to define a strategy for supporting new countries willing to volunteer with limited resources.

Properly supporting adequate training programs is also important in the area of offline software. Some initiatives in the scope of the HSF training program are very popular and received very good reviews from the WLCG scientific referees. They complement the experiment-specific programs well. What is missing today is more connection to the universities and laboratories to support proper careers as scientific software developers. The Software Institute for Data Intensive Sciences (SIDIS) had the ambition to facilitate this process. ECFA is establishing an academic program for detector technologies and could consider a similar initiative for software development.

[IMPACT-3] WLCG to continue pursuing the objective of establishing proper career opportunities for scientific software development, creating synergies with other sciences and leveraging existing organisations such as ECFA and national training programs.

[IMPACT-4] WLCG to review the format of the WLCG Workshop, offering the opportunity for the community to present new ideas, for example through lightning talks and poster sessions.

[IMPACT-5] WLCG to maintain a list of job opportunities at institutes willing to advertise the openings. This will hopefully allow us to retain expertise in the community and attract new ones.